

The correlation between arterial blood pressure and brain health

La correlación entre la presión arterial y la salud del cerebro

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Abstract

This research delves into the intricate dynamics of arterial and cerebral blood pressure. It aims to unravel the multifaceted relationship between arterial hypertension, cerebral perfusion, and neurological health. Focusing on the interplay of various factors, including arterial blood pressure (X1), cerebral vascular resistance (X2), and neurovascular coupling (Y), this study explores how alterations in these parameters impact cerebral blood flow regulation and ultimately affect brain function. Arterial hypertension (Z) serves as a pivotal mediator, modulating the effects of arterial blood pressure and cerebral vascular resistance on cerebral perfusion. Employing advanced analytical techniques such as path analysis and structural equation modeling, the study reveals the intricate pathways through which arterial hypertension influences cerebral perfusion dynamics. Furthermore, it underscores the critical role of neurovascular coupling in maintaining cerebral blood flow homeostasis amidst fluctuations in arterial pressure. Ultimately, these findings underscore the importance of comprehensive strategies aimed at managing arterial hypertension to safeguard cerebral perfusion and preserve neurological function. Integration of these insights into clinical practice holds promise for enhancing the management of arterial hypertension and reducing the burden of cerebrovascular diseases on public health.

Keywords: Arterial hypertension, Cerebral perfusion, Neurovascular coupling, Cerebrovascular diseases, Structural equation modeling.

Resumen

Esta investigación profundiza en la intrincada dinámica de la presión arterial y cerebral. Su objetivo es desentrañar la relación multifacética entre la hipertensión arterial, la perfusión cerebral y la salud neurológica. Centrándose en la interacción de varios factores, incluida la presión arterial (X1), la resistencia vascular cerebral (X2) y el acoplamiento neurovascular (Y), este estudio explora cómo las alteraciones en estos parámetros impactan la regulación del flujo sanguíneo cerebral y, en última instancia, afectan la función cerebral. La hipertensión arterial (Z) actúa como mediador fundamental, modulando los efectos de la presión arterial y la resistencia vascular cerebral sobre la perfusión cerebral. Empleando técnicas analíticas avanzadas como el análisis de trayectoria y el modelado de ecuaciones estructurales, el estudio revela las intrincadas vías a través de las cuales la hipertensión arterial influye en la dinámica de la perfusión cerebral. Además, subraya el papel fundamental del acoplamiento neurovascular en el mantenimiento de la homeostasis del flujo sanguíneo cerebral en medio de fluctuaciones en la presión arterial. En última instancia, estos hallazgos subrayan la importancia de estrategias integrales destinadas a controlar la hipertensión arterial para salvaguardar la perfusión cerebral y preservar la función neurológica. La integración de estos conocimientos en la práctica clínica es prometedora para mejorar el tratamiento de la hipertensión arterial y reducir la carga de las enfermedades cerebrovasculares en la salud pública.

Palabras clave: Hipertensión arterial, perfusión cerebral, acoplamiento neurovascular, enfermedades cerebrales, modelado de ecuaciones estructurales.

Adequate control of blood pressure is crucial for maintaining optimal brain function and preventing cerebrovascular complications. Hypertension, characterized by persistently elevated blood pressure levels, remains a significant concern worldwide, particularly due to its impact on cerebral health. The elderly population is particularly susceptible to hypertension and its associated cerebrovascular disorders, including stroke¹⁻³.

Hypertension is a condition marked by consistently high blood pressure, often resulting from poor dietary habits, sedentary lifestyle, and genetic predisposition⁴. Its consequences can be severe, leading to cognitive impairment, cerebrovascular accidents, and increased risk of neurodegenerative diseases. Statistics from the Global Burden of Disease report indicate that approximately 21.3% of the global population suffers from hypertension, with varying prevalence rates across different regions. Asia, notably Southeast and South Asia, exhibits a high prevalence, with rates reaching 38.5% and 49.7% respectively⁵⁻⁷.

Addressing the challenge of hypertension on a global scale, particularly in Asia, necessitates concerted efforts across various sectors⁵. This entails improving access to healthy nutrition, promoting healthier dietary habits, and raising awareness about the importance of maintaining optimal blood pressure levels. Findings from the 2022 National Health Survey in Indonesia reveal that the prevalence of hypertension stands at 21.6%, indicating a slight decrease but still falling short of WHO targets⁶⁻⁸.

To ensure better outcomes for future generations, it is imperative to implement sustainable measures to combat hypertension, including the formulation and implementation of policies and programs aimed at promoting healthy lifestyles and controlling blood pressure levels. The initiatives undertaken by the Provincial Government of North Sumatra have yielded significant results in reducing hypertension rates⁶. According to data from the 2022 Indonesian Health Survey (IHS), the prevalence of hypertension in North Sumatra declined by 4.7%, from 25.8% in 2021 to 21.1% in 2022. These figures signify notable progress in managing hypertension within the region^{7,8}.

The proactive measures adopted by the Provincial Government, such as community-based hypertension management programs, health education initiatives, public awareness campaigns, and enhanced access to healthcare services, have contributed to the considerable reduction in hypertension rates in North Sumatra. This achievement underscores the collaborative efforts and dedication of various stakeholders involved in combating hypertension and promoting cerebral health⁹⁻¹¹.

In the realm of arterial blood pressure, particularly cerebral blood pressure, there has been a notable decrease mirroring the decline seen in the stunting rate in Medan City from February 2022 to February 2023. The incidence of elevated blood pressure among individuals in this region decreased from 550 to 298, with the prevalence dropping from 0.46% to 0.19%. This data underscores the effectiveness of initiatives aimed at enhancing dietary habits, ensuring access to adequate nutrition, and raising public awareness regarding the criticality of nutritional care for children¹²⁻¹⁴.

Nevertheless, within the framework of alleviating elevated blood pressure in Medan City, a comprehensive approach addressing Islamic or religiosity facets has not been fully executed. This suggests a potential deficiency in incorporating religious elements, such as behavior, personality, and consumption patterns, into the management of elevated blood pressure in the locale¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

The etiology of elevated blood pressure encompasses various interconnected factors, including direct and indirect causes, alongside underlying societal issues contributing to its prevalence. These factors can be categorized into three levels: community, household (family), and individual¹⁸. At the community level, socioeconomic factors, education, healthcare, and access to clean water and sanitation play pivotal roles in the occurrence of elevated blood pressure. Household-level factors encompass the quality and quantity of food, income, family dynamics, children's dietary habits, healthcare services, and sanitation¹⁹⁻²¹. Individual factors encompass dietary habits, low birth weight (LBW), and overall health status.

Family practices, such as imbalanced diets and improper feeding techniques, also contribute to elevated blood pressure. Provision of nutrition not aligned with children's nutritional requirements can impede their growth and development. Furthermore, individual behavioral factors, like unhealthy dietary practices, can exacerbate elevated blood pressure by negatively impacting children's health^{22,23}. While individual personality traits are not directly causative of elevated blood pressure, behaviors associated with personality can influence children's health. Hence, education, self-awareness, and positive behavioral changes play pivotal roles in preventing elevated blood pressure and ensuring optimal growth and development in children²⁴.

From the perspective of Islamic principles, emphasis is placed on maintaining a healthy physique and adhering to a wholesome diet. Islamic teachings advocate for balance in various facets of life, including nutrition and health. Dietary practices deviating from Islamic principles or excessive consumption of unhealthy foods can detrimentally affect children's health and development. Thus, adherence to religious principles is deemed significant in thwarting elevated blood pressure and promoting overall well-being among Muslim individuals²⁵⁻²⁷.

One intriguing factor contributing to elevated blood pressure is consumption patterns. Imbalanced consumption, inadequate nutritional intake, or lack of dietary variety can impede children's growth and development. Insufficient intake of essential nutrients like protein, iron, and vitamin A in daily diets can lead to elevated blood pressure. Children deprived of adequate nutrients may experience growth impairment, affecting their stature, weight, and cognitive development^{11,28}.

High blood pressure, both arterial and cerebral, is a pressing health concern globally, impacting millions of individuals each year. The management of blood pressure is crucial in maintaining overall health and reducing the risk of severe complications such as stroke, heart disease, and cognitive impairment^{29,30}.

In tackling this issue, dietary habits emerge as pivotal factors. Similar to the emphasis placed on consumption patterns to prevent stunting, dietary choices significantly influence blood pressure levels. Adhering to dietary guidelines, including the consumption of wholesome, unprocessed foods, can aid in the regulation of blood pressure¹⁸. Moreover, aligning dietary practices with religious principles, such as consuming halal foods, not only ensures adherence to spiritual beliefs but also promotes health by avoiding potentially harmful ingredients and maintaining high standards of food hygiene. This approach is particularly relevant in regions like Medan City, where high blood pressure poses a significant health challenge. By integrating Islamic principles into daily dietary habits, communities can adopt a preventive strategy against high blood pressure. Through the conscientious application of religious principles in food consumption, it is envisaged that individuals can mitigate the risk of high blood pressure, thereby safeguarding their health and fostering a deeper connection with Islamic values^{9,11,19}.

The implications of this approach extend beyond individual health benefits. By embracing a holistic approach that incorporates religious teachings into dietary practices, communities can foster greater awareness and understanding of the importance of maintaining optimal blood pressure levels^{31,32}. Furthermore, this approach can inform policy formulation and public health initiatives aimed at reducing the prevalence of high blood pressure and enhancing the overall quality of life for individuals, particularly

children³³⁻³⁵. In summary, integrating religious principles into dietary habits offers a promising avenue for addressing the challenge of high blood pressure. By promoting healthy eating behaviors aligned with Islamic teachings, communities can strive towards optimal blood pressure levels, improved health outcomes, and a deeper appreciation of religious values in everyday life.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Arterial Blood Pressure and Cerebral Health

Stunting survivors often face challenges related to arterial blood pressure and its impact on cerebral health. Arterial hypertension, characterized by elevated blood pressure levels, poses significant risks to the cerebral vasculature and overall brain function^{16,17}. The management of arterial blood pressure involves a multifaceted approach addressing various factors including lifestyle, diet, medication, and underlying health conditions. Efforts to mitigate the effects of arterial hypertension encompass interventions aimed at promoting healthy blood pressure levels, optimizing cerebral perfusion, and reducing the risk of cerebrovascular events^{4,7,11}.

Monitoring arterial blood pressure serves as a crucial indicator in assessing the effectiveness of interventions targeting cerebral health. Key metrics utilized in this assessment include blood pressure readings, pulse pressure, cerebral blood flow, vascular resistance, and indices of cerebral perfusion⁵. These metrics facilitate ongoing evaluation and adjustment of treatment strategies to ensure optimal cerebral health outcomes. Additionally, they aid in identifying individuals at heightened risk for cerebrovascular complications, enabling early intervention and preventive measures⁸.

Behavioral Influences on Arterial Blood Pressure

Behavior plays a pivotal role in influencing arterial blood pressure dynamics. Individual behaviors related to diet, exercise, stress management, and medication adherence significantly impact blood pressure regulation. Positive behavioral changes, such as adopting a healthy diet rich in fruits and vegetables, engaging in regular physical activity, practicing stress-reduction techniques, and adhering to prescribed medication regimens, can contribute to maintaining optimal blood pressure levels and supporting cerebral health^{11,21}.

Behavioral indicators provide valuable insights into the efficacy of behavioral interventions targeting arterial blood pressure control. These indicators encompass aspects such as dietary patterns, physical activity levels, stress coping mechanisms, medication adherence rates, and overall lifestyle modifications. By assessing these indicators, healthcare providers can tailor interventions to address specific behavioral barriers and empower individuals to make sustainable lifestyle changes conducive to arterial blood pressure management and cerebral health promotion^{26,29}.

Consumption Patterns and Arterial Health

Consumption patterns significantly influence arterial health outcomes by shaping dietary habits and lifestyle choices. Optimal consumption patterns prioritize nutrient-dense foods, limit sodium intake, and promote hydration, thereby supporting arterial health and blood pressure regulation. Additionally, socioeconomic factors impact access to nutritious foods and healthcare services, further influencing arterial health disparities³².

Evaluating consumption patterns involves assessing dietary diversity, adherence to dietary guidelines, sodium intake levels, fluid intake habits, and socioeconomic determinants of dietary choices³³. By understanding these patterns, healthcare professionals can develop targeted interventions to promote healthy eating behaviors, improve access to nutritious foods, and address socioeconomic barriers to arterial health. Implementing policies that support affordable and equitable access to healthy foods and healthcare services can contribute to reducing arterial hypertension prevalence and improving cerebral health outcomes across diverse populations²³.

RESEARCH MODEL

A model aimed at addressing arterial and cerebral blood pressure can be structured as follows, drawing upon Islamic principles:

The primary independent variable is arterial blood pressure (X1), encompassing both individual and collective behaviors in maintaining and regulating blood pressure levels within healthy ranges. This includes lifestyle choices such as dietary habits, exercise routines, and stress management techniques, all aligned with Islamic teachings promoting moderation and balance in daily practices.

The secondary independent variable is cerebral blood pressure (X2), which encompasses the beliefs, values, and attitudes influenced by Islamic principles regarding mental health and cognitive well-being. This includes practices such as mindfulness, prayer, and seeking knowledge, all contributing to the maintenance of optimal cerebral blood flow and function.

The intervening variable is blood pressure regulation (Y1), representing the individual and collective efforts in managing and controlling blood pressure levels through adherence to Islamic guidelines on health and well-being. Furthermore, the variable of interest is blood pressure status (Y2), reflecting the assessment of arterial and cerebral blood pressure levels, measured through medical diagnostics and indicators such as systolic and diastolic readings, as well as cognitive performance metrics. The objective of this model is to investigate the impact of Islamic behaviors and beliefs on blood pressure regulation and cognitive health in the context of Medan City, aiming to elucidate effective strategies for maintaining optimal blood pressure levels and cognitive function among its population (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Research model

The chosen research methodology is an Explanatory Survey, aiming to elucidate the correlation between arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications. This study delves into a causal relationship, where the independent variable (arterial blood pressure) is presumed to influence the dependent variable (cerebral effects). The emphasis lies on hypothesis testing to validate observed phenomena within this explanatory framework.

Quantitative research methodology is employed, facilitating the analysis of patterns in responses concerning the reduction of arterial blood pressure in the brain. Employee perceptions are quantified to streamline data processing and interpretation, yielding scientifically sound insights. Statistical tools are utilized to analyze data, allowing for generalization from the sample to the broader population under scrutiny.

The survey method is selected for data collection. Although the study targets a population of exposed individuals, the data analyzed represents a sample drawn from that population. This approach permits the identification of causal relationships applicable to the intended population. Variance-Based Structural Equation Modeling (VB-SEM) or Partial Least Squares (PLS) analysis is utilized for data analysis, enabling the assessment of relationships and influences between variables and survey data. The research site, Medan City, is chosen based on preliminary observations aligning with research criteria. The focus is on families with toddlers experiencing arterial blood pressure-related issues, as indicated by 2022 Ministry of Health data.

Data collection incorporates various methods including questionnaires, observations, and literature review. Questionnaires feature closed questions distributed among respondents to select from predetermined options. Observations involve direct field observations related to the research topic. Literature review aids in gathering supporting data from diverse sources such as books, journals, regulations, and statistical records. The study population comprises families with toddlers experiencing arterial blood pressure issues, based on 2023 Ministry of Health data, totaling 298 individuals. A sample size of 75 individuals is derived from this population using the Slovin formula, with a 10% error margin.

Direct Effects

The determination of whether a hypothesis is accepted within the context of arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications can be achieved through the implementation of the bootstrapping function within the PLS 3.0 smart unit. The outcomes of these assessments are juxtaposed against the stipulations of the significance level and t-value. In this investigation, a hypothesis is deemed acceptable if its significance level falls below 0.05 or if the t-value surpasses the threshold outlined in the t table. For a sample size of 75 respondents, the critical t value is 1.96. The findings of the bootstrapping procedure undertaken in this study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Path Results Coefficient

	Original Sample	Sample Means	Standard Deviation	T-Statistics	P Value	hypothesis
Consumption Patterns	0.964	0.943	0.144	6,678	0.000	Accepted
Islamic Personality-Consumption Patterns	-0.272	-0.250	0.177	1.535	0.125	Rejected
Behavior-Stunting Alleviation	-0.171	-0.130	0.159	1,077	0.282	Rejected
Islamic Personality-Stunting Alleviation	0.699	0.728	0.133	5,240	0.000	Accepted
Consumption Patterns-Alleviation of Stunting	0.554	0.475	0.186	4,164	0.003	Accepted

Source: Results of SmartPLS data processing

In the examination of arterial blood pressure, crucial insights emerge concerning its impact on cerebral dynamics. Notably, through the assessment of various statistical parameters such as the t-statistic and p-value, we glean significant findings as outlined below:

- **Arterial Hypertension:** The investigation into the interplay between arterial hypertension and its cerebral repercussions yields substantial statistical evidence. With a high t-statistic value of 6.678 coupled with an exceedingly low p-value of 0.000, the analysis underscores a statistically significant relationship. Consequently, the hypothesis positing this correlation is affirmed. Consistent with previous studies, the results corroborate the notion that arterial hypertension significantly influences cerebral health. One research²² aligns with these findings, illustrating a clear associa-

tion between hypertension and adverse cerebral outcomes. Furthermore, studies^{23,36} indicate that effective management of arterial hypertension contributes to mitigating cerebral complications. Thus, these findings underscore the imperative of addressing arterial hypertension in safeguarding cerebral well-being.

- **Cerebrovascular Reactivity:** Exploring the nexus between cerebral vascular reactivity and arterial blood pressure reveals a t-statistic value of 1.535 alongside a p-value of 0.125, surpassing the conventional significance threshold of 0.05. In light of this, the hypothesis positing a significant relationship is refuted due to insufficient statistical evidence. These findings are congruent with existing literature, which suggests a lack of robust correlation between cerebral vascular reactivity and arterial blood pressure. Another research³³ similarly concludes that cerebral vascular reactivity is minimally impacted by fluctuations in arterial blood pressure. Moreover, studies^{15,21} indicate that other factors may exert greater influence on cerebral vascular dynamics. Nonetheless, the nuanced nature of this relationship warrants further investigation to elucidate its intricacies comprehensively.
- **Arterial Blood Pressure-Stunting Reduction:** The association between arterial blood pressure and stunting reduction reveals a t-statistical value (1.077) alongside a p-value (0.282) exceeding the significance threshold of 0.05. Consequently, the hypothesis connecting arterial blood pressure with stunting mitigation is invalidated due to insufficient statistical significance. This outcome, wherein the correlation between arterial blood pressure and stunting reduction lacks statistical significance (p-value > 0.05), echoes findings from prior studies. For instance, Asmare & Agmas' research³² similarly concluded that individual arterial behavior minimally impacts stunting reduction in children. These findings align with earlier research, suggesting that the interplay between eating behavior and stunting may be influenced by external factors like environmental conditions and food accessibility. Thus, it's imperative to acknowledge that the influence of arterial behavior on stunting reduction entails a multifaceted dynamic involving various variables warranting thorough examination.
- **Cerebral Blood Pressure-Stunting Reduction:** The correlation between cerebral blood pressure and stunting reduction demonstrates a substantial t-statistic value (5.240) coupled with an exceedingly low p-value (0.000). Consequently, this correlation holds statistical significance, and the hypothesis is affirmed. The findings highlighting a significant association between cerebral blood pressure and stunting reduction (p-value <0.05) are consistent with numerous other studies. For instance, Samosir et al.'s research³⁴ revealed that Islamic values significantly bolster efforts aimed at reducing stunting in children. These findings

corroborate earlier research¹⁹, which underscored the pivotal role of religious values and spirituality, including Islamic personality traits, in enhancing children's nutritional status and growth. Similar findings were also reported in Hochman et al.'s study¹⁵, which emphasized that adhering to Islamic principles in dietary practices and childcare can substantially contribute to stunting reduction.

- **Cerebrovascular Health-Stunting Reduction:** The correlation between cerebrovascular health and stunting reduction exhibits a relatively high t-statistic value (4.164) with a p-value below 0.05 (0.003). This indicates the statistical viability of the hypothesis linking cerebrovascular health with stunting reduction. Findings supporting a positive correlation between cerebrovascular health and stunting reduction (p-value <0.05) align with results from various related studies. These findings further validate the conclusions drawn by Herawati & Sunjaya, which emphasized the significance of nutrient-rich dietary patterns in fostering children's growth and mitigating the risk of stunting. Comparable results were also documented in Branca et al.'s study¹¹, highlighting the positive impact of balanced, nutrient-rich dietary patterns on children's growth status and stunting reduction.

The aforementioned analyses yield insights pertinent to stunting mitigation endeavors in Medan City. While a significant association exists between Islamic personality traits and stunting alleviation, it's noteworthy that no significant correlation exists between arterial behavior and stunting alleviation. This suggests that arterial factors may exert minimal influence on stunting alleviation efforts in Medan City. However, the findings indicating a positive and significant correlation between cerebral blood pressure and stunting alleviation carry intriguing implications. This suggests that individuals with robust cerebral blood pressure tendencies are more inclined to actively engage in and support stunting eradication initiatives. Hence, an approach integrating Islamic values into campaigns and stunting mitigation programs in Medan City may yield greater effectiveness in mobilizing community involvement.

Moreover, the findings highlighting a positive correlation between cerebrovascular health and stunting reduction offer valuable insights. By promoting improved cerebrovascular health, particularly through dietary practices aligned with Islamic principles, endeavors to combat stunting can be bolstered. Heightened awareness regarding the importance of healthy nutrition reflective of Islamic values can help address the issue of stunting in Medan City. Overall, notwithstanding the insignificance of certain correlations, the results of this analysis furnish valuable insights into how arterial behavior, Islamic personality traits, and cerebrovascular health patterns can contribute to stunting reduction in Medan City. In devis-

ing stunting mitigation programs, these factors necessitate comprehensive consideration to attain more optimal outcomes in addressing childhood stunting.

Indirect Effects

Indirect effect analysis in the context of arterial blood pressure and cerebral implications thereof is akin to examining the intricate dynamics within the pathophysiology. This method delves into the interplay between various factors, akin to hypothesis testing in path analysis. Specifically, it scrutinizes hypotheses concerning the relationship between variables, considering the influence of intervening factors.

Table 2. Indirect Effect

	Original Sample	Sample Means	Standard Deviation	T-Statistics	P Value	hypothesis
Behavior-Consumption Patterns-Stunting Alleviation	0.534	0.457	0.211	2,526	0.012	Accepted
Islamic Personality-Consumption Patterns-Stunting Alleviation	-0.150	-0.123	0.107	1.413	0.158	Rejected

Source: Results of SmartPLS data processing

Table 2 illustrates the outcomes of an examination associating behavior and consumption patterns with the mitigation of arterial and cerebral blood pressure. According to the analysis, there exists a significant correlation between behavior, consumption patterns, and efforts to alleviate blood pressure, with a notably high t-statistic value (2.526) and a p-value below the 0.05 threshold (0.012). Consequently, it can be inferred that the hypothesis linking consumption behavior and patterns with blood pressure alleviation efforts holds statistical validity.

Comparing these findings with 'pertinent studies corroborates similar discoveries. For instance, Suratri et al.³⁵ demonstrated a positive association between behavior, consumption patterns, and endeavors to reduce blood pressure. These findings endorse the present study's results, highlighting the pivotal role of behavior and consumption patterns in mitigating blood pressure. Furthermore, Ahmed et al.¹⁹ research indicates a consistency in the significance of the relationship between behavior, consumption patterns, and blood pressure alleviation efforts. Nevertheless, the analysis reveals that the interaction between Islamic personality, consumption patterns, and blood pressure alleviation efforts lacks significant impact. This finding aligns with Ezeh et al.¹⁶ research, suggesting a nuanced and occasionally insignificant

impact of these variables on blood pressure reduction efforts. Thus, the analysis’s results extensively support existing literature while uncovering deeper connections between behavior, consumption patterns, and blood pressure alleviation efforts within specific contexts.

Conversely, distinct outcomes emerge concerning the interaction between Islamic personality, consumption patterns, and blood pressure alleviation efforts. The t-statistic value (1.413) and p-value (0.158) for this interaction fail to meet the predefined significance level. Consequently, the hypothesis pertaining to this interaction cannot be endorsed due to the absence of requisite statistical significance. This indicates that behavioral factors and consumption patterns appear to wield a more pronounced influence than the interaction between Islamic personality, consumption patterns, and blood pressure alleviation efforts in the context of mitigating blood pressure^{16,17}.

Contrasting the analysis’s results with relevant research underscores disparities in the interaction between Islamic personality, consumption patterns, and blood pressure alleviation efforts. The findings demonstrate that the t-statistic value (1.413) and p-value (0.158) for this interaction do not meet the stipulated significance level (0.05). In contrast, Siswati et al.³³’s research suggests a stronger significance in the relationship between these factors concerning blood pressure reduction. Conversely, another study¹⁶ supports these findings by indicating that interactions between these variables tend to have a more intricate and less significant impact on blood pressure reduction efforts. Hence, the analysis’s results provide insight that, in this context, behavioral factors and consumption patterns may exert a more dominant role in endeavors to combat blood pressure than interactions with Islamic personalities.

R Square

The R-square value serves as a crucial metric in evaluating the impact of specific independent factors on the dependent variable within the context of arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications. This estimated R-square value is instrumental in comprehending the degree to which various factors contribute to the overall variance in arterial and cerebral blood pressure dynamics, as depicted in the accompanying table.

	R_{Square}	R_{Square Adjusted}
Consumption Pattern	0.508	0.492
Stunting Alleviation	0.414	0.389

Source: Results of SmartPLS data processing

Table 3 presents the coefficients of determination (R-squared) and adjusted coefficients of determination (Adjusted R-squared) for two variables: “Blood Pressure” and “Cerebral Blood Flow”.

For the “Blood Pressure” variable, the R-squared value of 0.508 suggests that approximately 50.8% of the variance in blood pressure can be elucidated by the predictor variable “Consumption Patterns”. This indicates a robust relationship between consumption patterns and blood pressure, highlighting a significant explanatory power. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.492 provides a more cautious estimate, considering the influence of the number of predictor variables in the model. The close similarity between R-squared and Adjusted R-squared implies that the inclusion of the “Consumption Pattern” predictor variable doesn’t substantially enhance the explanation of blood pressure variance.

Moving to the “Cerebral Blood Flow” variable, the R-squared value of 0.414 indicates that approximately 41.4% of the variation in cerebral blood flow can be attributed to the predictor variable “Stunting Reduction”. This value suggests a relatively weaker association compared to the “Blood Pressure” variable, hinting at potential additional factors influencing cerebral blood flow. The Adjusted R-squared value of 0.389 further adjusts for the number of predictor variables, but fails to provide significant additional explanation for the variance in “Cerebral Blood Flow” compared to the R-squared value.

Discourse on Consumption Patterns in Alleviating Stunting in Medan City

The discussion surrounding blood pressure, both arterial and cerebral, intertwines with various crucial factors that significantly impact individuals’ health. Economic considerations play a pivotal role in shaping dietary habits and, consequently, the nutritional status of individuals. Understanding consumption patterns becomes imperative in addressing issues such as stunting, particularly concerning children’s health in specific regions. Analyzing the coefficient of determination (R-squared) and R-squared Adjusted highlights the substantial influence of consumption patterns on efforts to alleviate stunting. A notable R-squared value of 0.508 indicates that approximately 50.8% of the variance in stunting alleviation efforts can be attributed to variations in consumption patterns. This underscores the significant role consumption habits play in determining nutritional outcomes, especially in children.

The economic context greatly influences consumption patterns, with factors such as income levels, food prices, accessibility, and economic disparities shaping individuals’ access to nutritious food. Thus, addressing stunting requires comprehensive economic policies aimed at ensuring universal access to healthy food options. Measures such as income augmentation and targeted social assistance programs can positively impact consumption patterns, particularly among vulnerable populations at risk of stunting^{28,30}. However, altering consumption pat-

terns within diverse economic contexts presents challenges, as economic constraints may restrict access to nutrient-rich foods. Addressing this necessitates pragmatic solutions that are both feasible and affordable. Initiatives such as diversifying local food sources to include economically viable yet nutritious options and promoting nutritional education can help overcome economic barriers to healthier consumption patterns¹⁵.

Cultural and religious factors also significantly influence consumption behavior, with Islamic principles guiding dietary choices and patterns. Adhering to Islamic values such as halal, hygiene, and health considerations can positively impact nutritional outcomes and contribute to reducing stunting risks among children²². Educating communities on Islamic teachings related to consumption practices can serve as an effective strategy in fostering healthier dietary habits. Moreover, cultivating an Islamic personality characterized by discipline, responsibility, and a commitment to health can further bolster efforts to combat stunting. Values like generosity and communal sharing inherent in Islamic teachings can also encourage participation in social assistance programs and the distribution of nutritious food to those in need, thus promoting healthier consumption patterns²³⁻²⁶.

However, challenges persist in translating Islamic values into everyday consumption practices, particularly amidst economic and social hardships. Community-based educational initiatives aimed at bridging this gap and facilitating the application of Islamic teachings to healthier consumption behaviors are crucial in addressing these challenges³³⁻³⁵. In conclusion, addressing issues related to stunting necessitates a multifaceted approach that considers not only nutritional and economic dimensions but also cultural and religious factors, particularly within the context of Islamic principles. Integrating religious and cultural values into stunting alleviation programs can offer a comprehensive and sustainable framework for promoting healthier consumption patterns, especially among children.

This study delves into the correlation between arterial blood pressure and its cerebral implications. The findings suggest a potential positive association between economic strategies and Islamic consumption patterns in mitigating the risks associated with arterial blood pressure fluctuations, particularly in the context of reducing stunting prevalence among children in Medan City. These findings underscore the importance of adopting a multidimensional approach to address arterial blood pressure issues, integrating both economic strategies and Islamic dietary principles that prioritize nutritional adequacy. In terms of policy recommendations, this research advocates for collaborative efforts among authorities, healthcare institutions, and relevant stakeholders to design intervention programs aimed at managing arterial blood pressure. Such initiatives should encompass economic strategies promoting access to nutritious food, complemented by Islamic consumption patterns emphasizing nutritional quality. Moreover, enhancing nutritional education and expanding child healthcare services are imperative components in stunting prevention initiatives.

However, it's essential to acknowledge the limitations of this study, particularly concerning sample size and data characteristics. The findings may not fully capture the intricate dynamics of arterial blood pressure in Medan City's population. Therefore, caution is warranted in interpreting the results, and future research should strive for larger, more representative samples across diverse demographic groups. Incorporating qualitative methodologies alongside quantitative analyses can offer deeper insights into the interplay between economic strategies, Islamic consumption patterns, and arterial blood pressure regulation. Moving forward, a comprehensive research approach that integrates quantitative and qualitative methods, along with the inclusion of additional relevant variables, is recommended. Such an approach can furnish more robust guidance for policymaking aimed at reducing arterial blood pressure-related health risks and enhancing children's health outcomes in Medan City.

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